

FROM INDEX LOCORUM TO CITATION NETWORK:
AN APPROACH TO THE AUTOMATIC
EXTRACTION OF CANONICAL REFERENCES AND
ITS APPLICATIONS TO THE STUDY OF CLASSICAL
TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

My research focusses on the automatic extraction of canonical references from publications in Classics. Such references are the standard way of citing classical texts and are found in great numbers throughout monographs, journal articles and commentaries.

In chapters 1 and 2 I argue for the importance of canonical citations and for the need to capture them automatically. Their importance and function is to signal text passages that are studied and discussed, often in relation to one another as can be seen in parallel passages found in modern commentaries. Scholars in the field have long been exploiting this kind of information by manually creating indexes of cited passages, the so-called *indices locorum*. However, the challenge we now face is find new ways of indexing and retrieving information contained in the growing volume of digital archives and libraries.

Chapters 3 and 4 look at how this problem can be tackled by translating the extraction of canonical citations into a computationally solvable problem. The approach I developed consists of treating the extraction of such citations as a problem of named entity extraction. This problem can be solved with some degree of accuracy by applying and adapting methods of Natural Language Processing. In this part of the dissertation I discuss the implementation of this approach as a working prototype and an evaluation of its performance.

Once canonical references have been extracted from texts, the web of relations between documents that they create can be represented as a network. This network can then be searched, manipulated, visualised and analysed in various ways. In chapter 5 I focus specifically on how this network can be leveraged to search through bodies of secondary literature. Finally in chapter 6 I discuss how my work opens up new research perspectives in terms of visualisation, analysis and the application of such automatically extracted citation networks.

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NOMENCLATURE

A&HCI	Arts and Humanities Citation Index 19, 20, 172
ACE	Automatic Content Extraction 113
ACL	Association for Computational Linguistics 113, 117
ANTLR	ANother Tool for Language Recognition 147, 148
APA	American Philological Association 77
APh	L'Année Philologique 6–9, 76, 89, 90, 92, 99, 105, 121, 122, 125–130, 143, 151, 164, 166, 168, 174, 175, 177, 179–185, 188
API	Application Programming Interface 5, 6, 79–84, 103, 104
BIBO	Bibliographic Ontology 75
BioNLP	Biomedical Natural Language Processing 117, 119
BiRO	Bibliographic Reference Ontology 75
BMCR	Bryn Mawr Classical Review 53, 54
Brat	Brat Rapid Annotation Tool 6, 7, 117, 122, 124, 131, 132, 135, 155
CFG	Context-free Grammar 147, 148
CIDOC	International Committee for Documentation 71
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model 5, 6, 62, 71, 72, 86, 88–91, 94, 96–100, 189
CiTO	Citation Typing Ontology 73–75
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure 192
CoNLL	Conference on Natural Language Learning 113, 119, 152
CRF	Conditional Random Fields 152–154
CS	Computer Science 60, 110, 120

CTS	Canonical Text Services 5, 6, 8, 43, 44, 71, 78–85, 88, 96, 98, 99, 102–104, 124, 143, 150, 157, 166, 170, 176, 189
CWKB	Classical Works Knowledge Base 5, 6, 76–78, 84, 85, 101, 103
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities 192
DEO	Discourse Elements Ontology 75
DH	Digital Humanities 15, 18, 19, 45, 170, 174
DoCO	Document Components Ontology 75
FaBiO	FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology 74, 90
FRBR	Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Record 5, 68–72, 74, 79, 90, 95, 99
FRBR _{ER}	FRBR Entity-Relationship 71, 72
FRBR _{OO}	FRBR Object-Oriented 6, 62, 71, 72, 86, 88–91, 97, 99, 100, 125, 189
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol 67, 68, 189, 192, 198
HuCit	Humanities Citation Ontology 6, 23, 49, 50, 52–54, 62, 63, 65, 68, 69, 76, 83, 85–101, 103, 104, 109, 189
ICOM	International Council of Museums 71
IE	Information Extraction 110, 113, 116, 117
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions 69
IOB	Input, Outside, Beginning 7, 131, 132
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation 7, 149, 150
LAWD	Linked Ancient World Data 76, 83
LAWDI	Linked Ancient World Data Institute 83, 84
LIS	Library and Information Science 18, 120, 172
LOD	Linked Open Data 66–68, 76, 83, 84, 100, 101, 192, <i>Glossary: Linked Open Data</i>
MaxEnt	Maximum Entropy 152–154
MUC	Message Understanding Conference 113, 119
NED	Named Entity Disambiguation 111

NER	Named Entity Recognition 21, 111, 113, 114, 119, 131, 152, 153, 165, 187, 188
NLP	Natural Language Processing 23, 63, 64, 110, 112, 113, 117, 119, 131, 132, 135, 147, 151, 162, 165
OCR	Optical Character Recognition 30, 43, 108, 126, 129, 130, 145
OED	Oxford English Dictionary 60
OWL	Web Ontology Language 65, 68, 88
PHI	Packard Humanities Institute 35, 42, 78
PoS	Part-of-speech 131, 134, 136, 137, 156, 157
RDF	Resource Description Framework 5, 6, 65–68, 76, 84, 90, 101, 102, 104, 105, 189
SAWS	Sharing Ancient Wisdoms 44, 84, 88
SCI	Science Citation Index 19, 172
SPAR	Semantic Publishing and Referencing 74
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol And RDF Query Language 65, 67
SQL	Structured Query Language 65
SVM	Support Vector Machines 152–154
SWAN	Semantic Web Applications in Neuromedicine 73–75
TAC	Text Analysis Conference 113
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative 43, 79, 82
TLG	Thesaurus Linguae Graecae 35, 38, 40, 43, 46, 70, 78
Turtle	Terse RDF Triple Language 6, 66, 85, 102, 105
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier 65–68, 84, 88, 189, 192, 198
URL	Uniform Resource Locator 77
URN	Uniform Resource Name 5, 6, 79, 80, 82–85, 88, 96, 98, 99, 102–104, 124, 143, 144, 150, 157, 166, 170, 176
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium 65, 101
XML	Extensible Markup Language 5, 6, 66, 81–83, 104

4

AUTOMATIC EXTRACTION OF CANONICAL CITATIONS

Overview

This chapter describes the approach I have developed to the automatic extraction of canonical citations. This approach consists of applying and adapting methods and techniques developed in Computer Science (CS) to the domain of Classics, and specifically to the problem of capturing references to ancient authors and texts. For this reason, in section 4.1 I introduce the key concepts of information extraction and the measures used to evaluate the results of this extraction. In section 4.2 I explain how my approach relates to past and ongoing research in the two sub-fields of CS, Information Extraction (IE) and Natural Language Processing (NLP). Section 4.3 describes the datasets that I created and mined for citations as part of this study. In section 4.4 I provide a detailed description of the sequence of steps involved in processing the data, the *pipeline*. Finally, in section 4.5 I discuss the results of the evaluation and consider ways in which the accuracy of the results could be improved.

4.1 KEY CONCEPTS IN INFORMATION EXTRACTION

4.1.1 *Extraction of Named Entities*

My approach to the extraction of canonical citations consists of adapting to the domain of Classics methods and techniques developed in CS to extract information from text. Therefore, before discussing in detail the extraction of citations, I explain how IE systems function by examining the working principles of a question answering system – i.e. a NLP

application that tries to answer questions formulated by users in natural language.¹

Consider the following passage drawn from the Wikipedia article on Aaron Swartz:

Two days after the prosecution rejected a counter-offer by **Swartz**, he was found dead in his **Brooklyn, New York** apartment, where he had hanged himself.

What are the steps required for a fictitious system to answer the question “Where did Aaron Swartz die?”² First, the named entities (highlighted in bold) need to be captured – i.e. “Swartz” and “Brooklyn, New York”, respectively the name of a person and of a geographical place. This operation, called Named Entity Recognition (NER), aims to gather the facts that enable the system to provide an answer to the question above. Second, one needs to make explicit what relations exist between parts of the text – co-reference resolution and relation detection – and what entities are referred to by names – Named Entity Disambiguation (NED).³

In this case, disambiguating the named entities means establishing that the name “Swartz” refers to Aaron Swartz the programmer and activist, not the actor, while resolving the co-references requires linking the name “Swartz” to the pronouns “he” and “his”. The assertion “was found dead in [...]” constitutes a relation existing between “Swartz” (the person) and “Brooklyn, New York” (the name of the place where he died), which also needs to be captured.

As I will articulate in section 4.4, I have applied this three-step process to the extraction of canonical citations. To capture such citations and their meaning I first extract from text the citation components, then I determine the relations that exist between these components and finally I disambiguate the extracted citations by assigning each of them the corresponding unique identifier.

¹ For a more comprehensive and detailed explanation of the concepts discussed in this section I refer the reader to Jurafsky and Martin (2009).

² I have deliberately left out the preprocessing steps, such as sentence segmentation and tokenisation, since they are of minor importance and will be addressed in section 4.4.

³ It can also be referred to as *named entity resolution*, *entity linking* or *normalisation*.

4.1.2 *Methods in Natural Language Processing*

The problem of extracting named entities from text, as any other NLP task, can be approached using different paradigms. The rule-based approach involves defining and applying a set of rules that signal the presence of a name (e.g. a name is a sequence of alphabetic characters that starts with a capital letter). In contrast, the machine learning approach consists of training a model to learn from a set of input examples what features characterise a named entity. The system I have developed to extract canonical references uses a mixture of rule-based and machine learning algorithms.

When talking about machine learning methods it is important to distinguish between *supervised* and *unsupervised* methods. The difference between these two methods is that supervised learning requires annotated and manually corrected data. There are also weakly supervised and semi-supervised methods, which both aim to reduce the amount of annotated data that is needed to train the model.

In this study I have adopted a supervised machine learning approach and applied it to the identification of named entities, a task consisting of assigning the correct named entity type to each word in a sentence. Supervised methods have been extensively applied to NLP tasks that entail some kind of classification such as detecting spam emails or tagging named entities. Supervised methods are suitable in cases where the expected output is already known as is the case with named entity recognition, which consists of assigning to each word in a sequence the corresponding named entity type drawn from a predefined set. Unsupervised methods are employed when one wants to elicit some patterns from the input data without making any assumptions concerning the output.

In my case I chose a supervised approach because when extracting named entities the expected output is already known. The main advantage of using such an approach is that the model can be re-trained with different training data. In the case of extracting citations, this means that the system can be trained to cope with the citation style characterising a specific set of documents. For example, given that different journals may differ as to how classical texts are cited, the system could be trained to capture the specificities of the citation style used by a given journal.

Supervised learning consists of training a statistical model to perform a given classification task such as assigning to each word in a sentence the corresponding named entity type. In order to predict the output, the model needs to be fed with training data where each instance to classify is associated with the corresponding label. By observing a number of features extracted from the training data the model is able to assign to each possible label a score indicating the probability of that label being assigned.

Three kinds of data are typically used in a supervised learning setting: the *training set*, which consists of data that is used to compute the probabilities; the *testing set*, which consists of unseen data used to evaluate the overall performance of the system (i.e. data that is not part of the training set); the *development set*, which consists of data different from the training and testing set. The development set is used to avoid the problem of overfitting, a situation in which the trained model performs poorly on data different from the training set. In section 4.3 I discuss the creation of an annotated training and test set for the specific task of extracting canonical citations from text.

4.1.3 Evaluation Metrics: Precision, Recall and F_1 Score

This section introduces the metrics that have been developed to evaluate the accuracy of information extraction systems. These metrics are used in section 4.5 to evaluate the system I have implemented to extract canonical citations.

NLP research is characterised by a strong focus on the evaluation of the various algorithms that can be employed to perform the same task. Since 1999 the Conference on Natural Language Learning (CoNLL) has been organising *shared tasks*, namely co-located events usually centered around one specific task (e.g. NER) in which the different systems developed by the participants are evaluated against the same data that is provided by the organisers.⁴ Some of these events, however, focus on specific disciplines: the 2013 Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL) conference, for example, featured the shared task “Corpus Anno-

⁴ The systematic evaluation of IE systems has been carried out at shared tasks organised in connection with events such as the CoNLL, the Message Understanding Conference (MUC), the Automatic Content Extraction (ACE) workshops and the Text Analysis Conference (TAC).

tation with Gene Regulation Ontology” which dealt with one specific aspect of extracting information from biomedical literature.

Error types

A key concept of evaluation is the classification of errors into different types. The error types vary in relation to the specific task that is being evaluated. In the following example I shall illustrate the types of errors that are encountered when evaluating the extraction of named entities. Let us suppose that our NER system has produced the output shown in figure 4.1. A comparison of the expected with the actual output shows that: the entity “Swartz” was correctly classified and is therefore a true positive (TP); “Two” was incorrectly recognised as a named entity thus constituting a false positive (FP); the entity “Brooklyn, New York” was missed by the system and is therefore a false negative (FN); all the other words that were correctly classified as not being named entities count as true negatives (TNs).

Evaluation of named entity extraction

Expected output:

Two days after the prosecution rejected a counter-offer by Swartz, he was found dead in his Brooklyn, New York apartment, where he had hanged himself.

Output:

Two days after the prosecution rejected a counter-offer by Swartz, he was found dead in his Brooklyn, New York apartment, where he had hanged himself.

Figure 4.1: Comparison of expected and obtained output for an example sentence showing the four error types: true positives are highlighted in green, false positives in yellow and false negatives in red; unhighlighted words are true negatives.

How do we transform these observations into numeric values that allow for comparison across different systems? This is done by means of standard metrics – *precision*, *recall* and F_1 *score*. These metrics take into account different combinations of the error types illustrated above in order to quantify slightly different aspects of the accuracy of the evaluated system. Figure 4.2 illustrates the four error types and how

they come into play when calculating the precision and recall metrics, which are introduced next.

Figure 4.2: Schematic illustration of the differences between the four error types and their relation to precision and recall from Walber (Own work) [CC-BY-SA-4.0], via Wikimedia Commons.

Precision

$$\text{Prec} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \quad (4.1)$$

Precision is defined by the formula in equation (4.1) and is the fraction of retrieved entities that are correct. This measure takes into account the correctly identified entities (TPs) as well as those that were mistakenly tagged as entities (FPs), but does not consider the entities that were missed (FNs). The precision of a system that produces the output of figure 4.1 is calculated as $\text{prec} = \frac{1}{1+3}$ and is therefore 0.25 (or 25%).

Recall

$$\text{Rec} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (4.2)$$

Recall is defined by the formula in equation (4.2) and is the fraction of correct entities that are retrieved by the system. Recall does not consider the FPs but, instead, takes into account the TNs, i.e. the entities that were missed – in this case the place name “Brooklyn, New York”. The recall given the output above is calculated as $\text{rec} = \frac{1}{1+1}$ and is 0.50 (or 50%) – in fact, out of two entities (i.e. “Swarz” and “Brooklyn, New York”) only one was correctly extracted.

F₁ Score

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2\text{PR}}{\text{P} + \text{R}} \quad (4.3)$$

Finally, the F_1 score (or F-measure) defined by the formula in equation (4.3) is a global metric that combines both precision and recall giving them equal importance. It is the weighted harmonic mean of precision and recall where the weight is expressed by the coefficient β : with $\beta < 1$ the precision is favoured, while with $\beta > 1$ the recall is favoured; a value of $\beta = 1$ treats them equally. F_1 indicates that the weight being used in the equation is 1. Therefore, the F_1 score of the system that produces the output above, given a precision of 0.25 and a recall of 0.50, would be $\text{F1} = (2 * 0.25 * 0.50) / 0.25 + 0.50$ thus 0.33 (or 33%).

4.2 THE LANDSCAPE OF INFORMATION EXTRACTION RESEARCH

This section aims to situate my research on the automatic extraction of canonical citations within the broader landscape of research on IE. First, I look at research on this topic in disciplines other than Classics. I then focus on domain-specific named entities and discuss some applications from Archaeology as well as from some more distant fields such as Biomedicine and Legal Studies. I conclude with a section on the extraction of modern bibliographic references by considering the similarities in terms of issues raised and solutions applied between this problem and the extraction of references to primary sources.

4.2.1 *Information Extraction Systems*

The origins of research on IE are found outside academia. IE systems were developed in the 1980s by the US Navy initially with the goal of extracting information from news and military texts (Grisham, 2010). However, in the last decade due to large scale digitisation initiatives and to the growing volume of publications being made available online the problem of finding scalable solutions to extracting information has become increasingly important in a number of disciplines. I now consider some IE systems that were developed both within and outside of the disciplines of Classics and Archaeology that are relevant to my approach.

Biomedicine, and specifically Biomedical Natural Language Processing (BioNLP), has been heavily investing in automatic information extraction. The proceedings of recent BioNLP workshops, which were co-located with the ACL conference, give an idea of the depth and breadth of research in this area (Cohen et al., 2013,0). The range of tasks covered spans the extraction of gene and protein names from biomedical texts to tasks focussed on very specific problems such as the shared task *Cancer Genetics*, which deals with the extraction of information from literature on cancer.⁵ Despite the distance between Classics and Biomedicine, my research benefitted from the results produced in this area in two respects: first, the Brat Rapid Annotation Tool (Brat) that I employed to annotate the data was developed within the BioNLP community (Stenertorp et al., 2012); second, the tool that achieved the greatest accuracy with regards to sentence segmentation – the task of splitting a text into sentences – was the one that is included in Brat.⁶

Further examples of information extraction systems can also be found in disciplinary areas closer to the Humanities. In the Fine Art domain, Odat et al. (2015) present a system for the extraction of information related to chemical processes and preservation treatments from unstructured texts related to the conservation of paintings. The solution they propose closely resembles the approach I am adopting. First, the system is based on an ontological *knowledge base* containing key concepts that describe paintings as well as the methods and techniques for their

⁵ Cancer Genetics (CG) task, <http://2013.bionlp-st.org/tasks/cancer-genetics>.

⁶ See section 4.4.1 for the problematic aspects of sentence segmentation when dealing with texts from Classics.

conservation. Second, a combination of machine learning-based and rule-based algorithms are used to capture the named entities and the relations existing between them. Third, entities and relations, once extracted from text, are mapped onto concepts and properties contained in the knowledge base. Finally, the results of the extraction allow users to search for publications related to a specific technique or issue in the art conservation domain.

Similar systems were also devised in the field of Archaeology with the goal of distilling specific pieces of information from unstructured texts. Paijmans and Wubben (2007), for example, focussed on the automatic indexing of archaeological papers and reports. They used a machine learning-based approach to capture chronological and geographical references and measurements. Following that, Byrne and Klein (2010) developed a system aimed at extracting event structures such as archaeological finds, excavations and surveys from text in order to transform the extracted information into semantic data.

Recent research in the field of Digital Classics has focussed on the extraction of one specific named entity type, namely geographic place names. This task is commonly known as *geoparsing* and, similar to what happens with other kinds of named entities, consists of the two separate steps of extracting and resolving place names.⁷ *Geoparsing*, also known as *geotagging*, deals with identifying chunks of texts that constitute place names, whereas *georesolution* consists of determining the most likely geographical location of each extracted place name.

The *geoparsing* of digitised texts was the main goal of the recently concluded Google Ancient Places (GAP) project (Isaksen et al., 2012). The project relied on the Edinburgh Geoparser for the *geotagging* step (Grover et al., 2010), while the *georesolution* was carried out by linking place names to matching entries in the Pleiades gazetteer of ancient places.⁸ The efforts initiated by GAP are now being continued by the project Pelagios⁹, which stands for Pelagios Enable Linked Ancient Geodata In Open Systems. Pelagios, which is in its third funding phase at the time of writing, also deals with *geoparsing* but with a specific focus on primary sources and tries to cover a wide range of traditions, both geographically and chronologically (Simon et al., 2012).

⁷ For a broader reflection on the history of the relationship between geography and computing in Classics see Elliott and Gillies (2009).

⁸ Pleiades, <http://pleiades.stoa.org/>.

⁹ Pelagios, <http://pelagios-project.blogspot.de>.

4.2.2 *Citations and other Discipline-specific Named Entities*

As pointed out in section 1.5, the idea of modelling canonical citations as named entities was first suggested by Crane et al. (2009). This approach follows the more general trend in NLP and NER research of extending the hierarchy and number of named entities to cover discipline-specific pieces of information (Nadeau and Sekine, 2007, pp. 2–4). This trend leads to the identification of more finely grained entities that are of interest to scholars within a specific domain: some examples of such domain-specific entities are discussed next.

The named entities that are common to both the MUC and CoNLL sets are Location, Person and Organization.¹⁰ The MUC set also contains the category Misc, which captures entities not falling into any of the categories above. CoNLL adds to the core set 4 more entities: Time, Money, Percent and Date. In addition to these general entities there exist named entities that capture concepts of interest within specific domains. The mentions of genes and proteins, for example, are considered as named entities in the field of BioNLP (Settles, 2004), while entities such as Judge, Attorney, Company, Jurisdiction and Court, which are more finely grained instantiations of the entities Person and Organisation, are useful when extracting information from legal texts.

The idea of treating references as if they were named entities is not totally unprecedented. Francesconi et al. (2010) extracted case citations from legal texts while Galibert et al. (2010) extracted references to patents. In both cases the identification of such references is necessary to create networks of citations between documents that allow for an effective means of finding information within large sets of legal or patent-related documents. The approach I have adopted, however, differs from these approaches insofar as I model a citation as a relation between citation components instead of treating it as a single, monolithic entity. In section 4.3.1, I explain my rationale for making this decision and discuss, by means of examples drawn from the annotated data, the benefits of my approach.

¹⁰ A fixed-space font is used throughout this chapter to indicate named entity types.

4.2.3 *The Extraction of Modern Bibliographic References*

Although the main focus of this dissertation is on canonical references there are other kinds of bibliographic references that can be extracted from texts such as those to modern publications. In this section I shall discuss research on the extraction of references to modern publications that is especially relevant in the context of this research, with a focus on the issues that are raised when working with humanities publications.

The extraction of references to secondary sources such as monographs, edited volumes and journal articles is an essential task to perform when creating citation indices like those that were considered in section 1.4.2 above. This task consists of two distinct operations: firstly, locating the references within the document and, secondly, parsing each reference in order to identify the various pieces of bibliographic information (e.g. author, title, publication date, etc.). In particular, making this process as automatic as possible is of great importance for the scalability of such endeavours, i.e. their ability to handle large sets of documents. As a result, there has been extensive research on this topic in CS over the last two decades starting with the seminal work by Giles et al. (1998) on an automatic citation indexing system for Citeseer. Citeseer is a citation index that primarily covers literature in CS and Library and Information Science (LIS). The current version of this index, called CiteSeer^x, relies on ParsCit¹¹ for the extraction of bibliographic references. My approach to extracting canonical citations, and particularly the feature set used for training the statistical model, was informed by the work done by Council et al. (2008) on the development of ParsCit (see section 4.4.2).

Furthermore, the high level of accuracy that current citation extraction systems are able to achieve has certainly contributed to their application in a variety of scenarios. The platform ResearchGate¹², for example, uses an indexing system called Grobid¹³ in order to extract automatically bibliographic references from the full text of publications that are authored by the users and uploaded to the platform (Lopez, 2009). One feature of this platform, which is enabled by such an indexing system, is the ability to connect with researchers that cite one's own publications.

¹¹ ParsCit, <http://aye.comp.nus.edu.sg/parsCit/>.

¹² ResearchGate, <http://researchgate.net/>.

¹³ Grobid, <http://github.com/kermitt2/grobid>.

Although several tools and services are available for the extraction of bibliographic references, the accuracy of these tools tends to worsen when they are applied to humanities publications. This is due to the fact that, up until now, most of the development of automatic citation indexing systems has taken place in the scientific domain. As a result, certain discipline-specific citation practices result in difficulties for these tools. A notable example is the extraction of those expressions which are usually found in footnotes and are used to refer to publications that have already been cited (e.g. “idem”, “ibidem”, “op. cit.”, “loc. cit.”, etc.). This issue is ultimately one of anaphora resolution: what needs to be established is to which one of the already cited items the anaphoric expression refers to (e.g. “idem”). In order for the anaphora to be resolved one needs to isolate similar expressions and maintain the precise order in which publications are cited in the text.

4.3 CREATION OF ANNOTATED DATASETS

Defining an annotation scheme is an essential part of the broader process of translating a specific problem or phenomenon into computational terms. Modelling the extraction of canonical citations as a named entity recognition task requires entities and relations to be established. The entities and relations that I have specified in my research in order to annotate canonical citations within the data manually and automatically are defined by the annotation scheme described in section 4.3.1.

In section 4.3.2 I provide some detailed information about the datasets that were used in this research – *L’Année Philologique* and JSTOR. Finally, the file formats that are used to store the annotated datasets are briefly illustrated in section 4.3.3. Understanding the scheme that was used to annotate the data is essential in order to understand the extraction pipeline described in section 4.4.

4.3.1 *A Scheme to Annotate Canonical Citations*

Named Entities

The annotation scheme comprises the following entities:

- Author: captures mentions of the name of an ancient author, e.g. “Xenophon”;

- Awork: captures the title of an ancient work, e.g. “Hellenica”;
- Refauwork: captures a structured reference to the cited work, where the structure is typically created by the use of punctuation and abbreviations. Refauwork can be used to tag a reference to an author (e.g. “Thuc.” for Thucydides), to a work (e.g. “Hell.” for Xenophon’s *Hellenica*) or to tag a sequence in which both author and title are indicated (e.g. “Xen., Hell.”). This entity was also devised to cover those cases where the abbreviation of the author’s name is used, in a sort of metonymy, to refer to the *opus maximum* or the only work written by a given author (e.g. “Thuc.” for Thucydides’ *Histories*);¹⁴
- Refscope: is used to annotate the scope of the citation, i.e. the precise indication of which section of a given work is being cited (e.g. the portion “3.3.1–4” of the citation “Hell. 3.3.1–4”).

In designing this scheme I examined a wide variety of citation examples so as to ensure that it can be used to annotate virtually *any* canonical citation. These examples – some of which were already discussed in section 2.1 and section 3.2 – represent diverse citation styles and cover a variety of citation practices ranging from the early modern to the contemporary.

Figure 4.3: An example of annotated APh document (75-0113) visualised in Brat: the highlighted portions of text indicate named entities, while the arrows represent the relations existing between them.

The visualisations that are provided throughout this section, such as the one in figure 4.3, were produced using Brat, which is the environment of choice for annotating and visually displaying the data. In such visualisations the named entities are indicated as spans of texts of different colours with a label to indicate the entity type (e.g. Refauwork).

¹⁴ For a definition of *opus maximum* see *infra* p. 52.

The relations between entities are represented as arrows connecting two or more entities with a label indicating the type of relation (e.g. *scope*).

Relations

Given these four entities, a canonical citation is defined as a binary relation between any two entities, where one entity must be by definition the indication of the citation's scope (*Refscope*) while the other can belong to any of the remaining entity types (*Aauthor*, *Awork* and *Refauwork*). figure 4.3 shows how the citations "Pliny, nat. 11,4,11 and 11,16,46" and "Vergil, georg. 4,149–218" can be represented as relations between their components.

There are two main reasons why it seemed preferable to model citations as relations between citation components rather than as single entities – as I had initially suggested elsewhere (Romanello et al., 2009c). This approach allows for better representing discursive citations, namely citations that are constituted by non consecutive tokens. An example of this kind of citation is provided in figure 4.4. Such a citation could not be captured by means of one single entity, which requires all tokens that constitute the citation to be consecutive. Instead, it can be represented as a relation between the author's name (i.e. "Ammianus") and the cited passages. It is also worth noting that the name "Ammianus" is used here in a metonymic way to refer to the work *Res Gestae*, his opus maximum.

The second reason for preferring this solution is that entities of the same type tend to be homogeneous in terms of the features they display: *Refscope* entities, for example, are mostly made of numbers and punctuation signs, whereas *Aauthor* and *Awork* entities almost never contain numbers and in most cases begin with a capital letter. When training a statistical model to recognise a set of entities, the model is more likely to achieve better results if each entity type is characterised by a relatively homogeneous set of features.

Disambiguation

In addition to extracting named entities and the relations between them, it is also important to make explicit what exactly is being referred to, an operation known as disambiguation. For example, the entity *Aauthor* identified by the string "Ammianus" in figure 4.4 refers to the ancient author Ammianus Marcellinus.

Figure 4.4: Representing canonical references as relations between named entities allows us to capture the discursive reference “Ammianus [...] (15, 8, 7) , and [...] (14, 10, 1-16 and 30, 3, 3-5)”, which is made up of non consecutive tokens.

A common approach to disambiguating named entities is to use links to Wikipedia pages as unique identifiers. This solution would be suitable when disambiguating ancient authors and their works but it would not be of much help when identifying specific sections of ancient works as there are no Wikipedia entries for each citable section of any ancient work. The solution I chose is to use the identifiers specified by the Canonical Text Services (CTS) protocol and based on the Uniform Resource Name (URN) syntax.¹⁵ For instance, Ammianus is identified by `urn:cts:latinLit:stoa0023`, his *Rerum Gestarum* has the CTS URN `urn:cts:latinLit:stoa0023.stoa001` and book 14, chapter 1 of this work can be referred to by the identifier `urn:cts:latinLit:stoa0023.-stoa001:14.1.1`.

Figure 4.5: This figure shows how a CTS URN is attached to the scope relation it disambiguates and is visualised on mouseover in Brat.

These identifiers are stored within the comment field attached to any given entity or relation in the annotated datasets (see figure 4.5). They disambiguate named entities by pointing to individuals that are con-

¹⁵ For further information on the CTS protocol see section 3.4.3.

tained in the knowledge base discussed in the previous chapter. For example, in table 4.1 the name “Ammianus” is assigned the identifier `urn:cts:latinLit:stoa0023`. Once this identifier is looked up in the knowledge base it becomes possible to derive the information that the entity thereby identified has the ontological class `frbroo:F10_Person` or, in other words, is a person as defined by the FRBR Object-Oriented (FRBR_{OO}) ontology.

Table 4.1: Mapping between strings, CTS identifiers and ontology classes for the named entities and relations contained in APh 75–00174 (the prefix `urn:cts:latinLit:` was stripped off from all identifiers in order to make the table more easily readable).

String	Type	Identifier	Ontology Class
Ammianus	Aauthor	stoa0023	frbroo:F10_Person
Vergil	Aauthor	phio690	frbroo:F10_Person
(Aen. 6,851–853)	Scope	phio690.phio03:6.851–6.853	hucit:TextElement
Ammianus (15,8,7)	Scope	stoa0023.stoa001:15.8.7	hucit:TextElement
Ammianus (14,10,1–16)	Scope	stoa0023.stoa001:14.10.1–14.10.16	hucit:TextElement
Ammianus (30,3,3–6)	Scope	stoa0023.stoa001:30.3.3–30.3.6	hucit:TextElement
Aeneid	Awork	phio690.phio03	frbroo:F1_Work

4.3.2 The Datasets: APh and JSTOR

This section aims to provide a rationale for choosing the datasets that I have used in my research and to highlight the differences between the datasets. Two corpora were identified for this purpose: one is made up of abstracts extracted from the analytic bibliography *L'Année Philologique* (APh) and the other consists of the journal articles in JSTOR that are related to Classics.

The selection was based on four criteria. First, the corpora had to be of essential importance to classical scholars. Given that the methods I have used in my research are likely to be unfamiliar to many classicists, I deliberately chose two well known resources. The second criterion was the size, which had to be challenging enough so as to justify an automatic approach to the data processing. Third, the chosen corpora needed to be significantly different in terms of the types of resources,

quality of the data and style of the citations they contained. Such differences were important in order to ensure the general applicability of the devised approach or, in other words, to avoid what in machine learning terms is known as *overfitting*, i.e. a situation in which a trained model performs well on the training set but performs poorly on unseen data. Fourth and last criterion was the language of the texts. The fact that English did not completely replace other European languages as a means of scholarly communication in the field of Classics makes covering as many of these languages as possible an important requirement.

In chapter 2 I discussed the importance of classical commentaries as a literary genre. However, I decided not to mine citations from them. The availability of commentaries is certainly not an issue as many of them, and particularly those that are already in the public domain, were recently made accessible in electronic format by large scale initiatives such as Google Books and the Internet Archive. However, the effort needed to prepare the data for processing made the mining of citations from digitised commentaries impracticable. In fact, the poor quality of the OCR of these texts, especially when they contain polytonic Greek, means that the OCR needs to be reperfomed in order to bring the texts to a state that is actually suitable for information extraction purposes.

Another disadvantage of working with commentaries is the complex layout structure that such texts present, often consisting of multiple columns or horizontal levels as shown in the example commentaries discussed in section 2.1. Such a complex layout structure is likely to cause some problems with the OCR and would require some structural markup in order to distinguish the various levels of text in the printed page. Despite the technical challenges they present, commentaries are an extremely interesting type of texts to extract canonical citations from.

L'Année Philologique (APh)

The first corpus I worked with consists of texts drawn from the APh. The APh is a critical and analytical bibliography that has been published annually since 1924 and indexes virtually any publication that has some relevance to research in Classics. It may be said without exaggeration that it constitutes the starting point for any research in this field. For each indexed publication the APh provides a short abstract summarising the topic covered as well as the main points discussed.

One essential characteristic of the APh is the abundance of canonical citations. Not every APh abstract, however, contains such citations. The abstract of a publication focussing on Archaeology, for instance, is more likely to contain references to museum objects than citations of texts. On the contrary, summaries of publications that focus on text often contain an indication of the main text passages that the authors discussed, these are signalled in the text by means of canonical citations.

Since the work of the reviewers is informed by the same abstracting guidelines, the style of canonical citations tends to be fairly homogeneous throughout the APh. Work titles, for example, are always enclosed by angle quotes called Guillemets (“«” and “»”). Moreover, the abstracts are written in the main European languages – i.e. French, Italian, Spanish, German and English – depending on the national office where the indexing and abstracting was carried out. In fact, the work of the APh is organised by means of a distributed network of national offices that are responsible for abstracting the publications and inputting the data into a central system ensuring the thorough coverage of this resource.

The first sampling decision I had to take, given the scale of this resource, was to work on one of the 80 annually published volumes. The 2004 volume – volume 75 – was chosen and this resulted in a dataset of 354,672 tokens. Since this dataset was still too large for manual correction, I had to apply a second sampling step to reduce the number of tokens to a manageable size (25,889 tokens, see table 4.2).

Table 4.2: Number of documents and tokens of the APh dataset. The dataset is divided into two subsets: the development set consisting of documents that were annotated automatically and the training set consisting of documents that were also manually checked.

Subset	Documents	Tokens
development set	6,947	354,672
training set	366	25,889
Total	7,313	380,561

The dataset was first automatically annotated according to the annotation scheme discussed in the previous section. The resulting annotations were then manually verified by two domain experts. An annotated and manually corrected corpus was required in my research for two reasons: first, to be used as the baseline when evaluating the accuracy with

which canonical citations can be extracted automatically and, second, to be used as input data to train a statistical model to capture named entities from text. Since this dataset is the first of its kind and given that annotating the data is a highly time consuming process, considerable efforts were made to make the corpus openly available so as to facilitate further research on this topic.¹⁶

The sampling method I used to reduce the number of tokens that had to be manually corrected without sacrificing the effectiveness of the corpus is called Active Annotation. Active Annotation is the adaptation of the Active Learning method (Settles, 2009) to the task of creating an annotated corpus; it was first proposed by Vlachos (2006) with relation to the task of tagging named entities in biomedical texts and has recently found application to humanities data (Ekbal et al., 2011).

This method has been found to reduce the effort of creating training material, which is a crucial bottleneck when adapting supervised learning methods to a new domain. The idea underlying Active Annotation is that, in order to reduce the amount of training data required, the documents for manual correction are carefully selected instead of being randomly sampled. What exactly does *carefully selected* mean in this context? The instances (i.e. sentences) are chosen based on how informative they are for the classifier. The instances with which the classifier had the greatest difficulties in predicting the correct label are selected. The informativeness of a given instance is quantified by a parameter called the *confidence interval*, which measures the degree of confidence of the classifier in making a certain prediction.

Table 4.3: Basic statistics about the training set derived from the APh dataset with the documents grouped by language.

Subset	Documents	Sentences	Tokens
train-de	39	72	2,664
train-en	65	208	6,231
train-es	32	59	2,444
train-fr	123	230	6,633
train-it	107	130	4,374
Total	7,312	699	25,889

¹⁶ The APh dataset was released under an open source licence and is available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12762>.

To sum up, Active Annotation was used to reduce the number of tokens to be manually annotated from 354,672 to 25,889. The breakdown of documents in the training set by language is shown in table 4.3, while table 4.4 summarises the number and type of annotations that were produced and manually corrected.

Table 4.4: Number and type of annotations contained in the APh training set.

Annotation	n
Aauthor	368
Awork	231
Refauwork	221
Refscope	441
Scope relation	381

JSTOR

A second dataset used while developing the citation extraction system consists of journal articles drawn from JSTOR. JSTOR is the most comprehensive single archive of journal articles related to Classics containing the full text of 171,000 articles belonging to some 1,456 journals for a total of more than 327 million tokens.¹⁷ I have used this dataset in order to guarantee that the system would also work on documents that differ from those contained in the training set or in other words to avoid overfitting.

The number of journals included and the timespan covered result in a wide diversity of citation styles. Processing a corpus of this scale represents a challenge in terms of time and computing power. At the same time, the scale makes JSTOR a unique resource to work with allowing us to track a given phenomenon, such as text reception, over a time span of more than two centuries.

The documents in my dataset are those articles contained in JSTOR that were classified as being related to Classics. Since the classification was performed automatically by using a clustering technique called Topic Modelling, the dataset does contain some documents that are not related to Classics and were incorrectly classified. As the content in JSTOR constantly grows and errors in the automatic classification may

¹⁷ Given the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) errors that are contained, this figure may not correspond to the number of actual tokens.

disappear, the dataset I have worked with needs to be understood as a snapshot of the data at a specific point in time.¹⁸

As far as the licence is concerned, for datasets of up to 1,000 documents the data can be freely obtained by using Data for Research¹⁹, an online tool that allows researchers to interact in various ways with JSTOR's content. If one needs to access a dataset that exceeds this limit, however, it is necessary to describe the research for which the data is being requested and, upon approval by JSTOR, to sign a licence agreement. This restricted licencing policy was, in fact, the main reason why the APh was preferred to JSTOR as a source of data to create a reusable dataset.

This corpus differs substantially from the one that was previously described in several respects. The first difference concerns the quality of the data: while the APh corpus consists of cleanly transcribed texts that were exported from a database, the data in the JSTOR corpus is often the result of OCR and because of this the quality is variable. Although the general approach was to accept the presence of OCR errors without trying to correct or recover them, in some cases dealing with these errors was unavoidable. This was the case, for example, with characters that were wrongly recognised by the OCR software and thus transcribed into random sequences of characters. Sometimes these characters would combine to form sequences that have a special function, thus causing problems with operations such as reading in the input files (e.g. the sequence “\n” indicates a new line).

Another difference is that the JSTOR articles come as plain text, i.e. without any kind of structural markup to distinguish between the different sections of an article (e.g. running headers, page numbers, footnotes, bibliography, etc.). What this means in practice is that, given that footnotes of articles in Classics tend to contain a wealth of canonical citations, without markup it is impossible to link such citations back to their original context. Moreover, running headers and page numbers become part of the text thus causing some noise that would be desirable to filter out. Similarly, given that citations to primary and secondary sources look relatively similar, not being able to isolate the bibliogra-

¹⁸ The dataset described in this section was created on November 26 2013 by JSTOR staff using the following request <<http://dfr.jstor.org/fsearch/submitrequest?fs=tom1:tgml&view=text&cc=subject:classicalstudies-discipline^1.0>>.

¹⁹ Data for Research, <http://dfr.jstor.org/>.

phy section from the rest of the article caused errors in the extraction of citations and named entities.

4.3.3 File Formats of the Datasets

Once annotated according to the scheme that was illustrated in section 4.3.1, the data was stored using two distinct file formats: the Input, Outside, Beginning (IOB) format and the standoff markup format used by the annotation environment Brat.

influenced	VBN	0
by	IN	0
Pliny	NP	B-REFAUWORK
,	,	I-REFAUWORK
nat.	NP	I-REFAUWORK
11	CD	B-REFSCOPE
,	,	I-REFSCOPE
4	CD	I-REFSCOPE
,	,	I-REFSCOPE
11	CD	I-REFSCOPE
and	CC	B-REFSCOPE
11	CD	I-REFSCOPE
,	,	I-REFSCOPE
16	CD	I-REFSCOPE
,	,	I-REFSCOPE
46	CD	I-REFSCOPE
and	CC	0

Figure 4.6: The annotation of a canonical reference represented in the IOB tabular format. The three columns contain respectively: the annotated token; its Part-of-speech (PoS) tag and the named entity label assigned to it.

IOB is a tabular format that is used in NLP for a variety of chunking tasks (e.g. NER). An IOB file, such as the one given in figure 4.6, contains one token per line with blank lines to indicate the boundaries between sentences; in turn, each line contains values that may be organised in multiple columns and are typically separated by means of the tab character (i.e. “\t”). The name of this file format derives specifically from the notation that is used to label the tokens: the letter 0 is used for tokens without a label; a label starting with prefix B- is used for the first token of an entity, whereas I- is used for all successive tokens.

The format used by Brat belongs to the category of standoff markup formats. The term *standoff markup* indicates that the annotations about the text – i.e. the named entity labels in the case of this study – are

stored separately from the text itself. An annotated span of characters is then identified by means of a numeric offset, i.e. a character index relative to the origin where the index of the first character of the document is 0. For example, the first row of the standoff markup displayed in figure 4.7 is to be read as “the span of text identified as T1 with start index 442 and end index 453, which corresponds to the string ‘Pliny, nat.’ has the label Refauwork”. A computer program that manipulates such annotations typically reads the text into an ordered list of characters – or array – then uses the character indexes to identify a given span of text. In the programming language Python, for example, assuming that the variable `document_text` is a list of characters representing the entire text of the document APh 75-0113, the notation `document_text[442:453]` selects the string of text corresponding to “Pliny, nat.”.

T1	REFAUWORK	442	453	Pliny, nat.
T2	REFSCOPE	454	463	11, 4, 11
T3	REFSCOPE	464	478	and 11, 16, 46
T4	REFAUWORK	483	497	Vergil, georg.
T5	REFSCOPE	498	509	4, 149-218.

Figure 4.7: The annotation of a canonical reference represented as standoff markup. The four columns contain respectively: the annotation identifier; the named entity label; the start and end index of the annotated string; the annotated portion of text.

The reason for keeping two distinct representations of the same data lies in the fact that different formats suit different tasks in different ways. Similarly, the decision about which formats to use is determined by the pieces of software or libraries used. In this specific case, the choice of using both the IOB and the standoff markup format was due to the fact that a tabular format such as IOB is an input format commonly accepted by NLP tools, whereas the latter is the format that Brat uses internally to store the annotated data. To keep these two representations of the same underlying data synchronised I had to carry out some additional operations that need careful testing as they may lead to the propagation of errors throughout the corpus.

4.4 THE INFORMATION EXTRACTION PIPELINE

In this section I provide a detailed description of the information extraction pipeline that I have implemented in order to capture canonical citations from the datasets that were just described.²⁰ The term *pipeline* emphasises the fact that the processing steps form a sequence where the output of the previously executed step constitutes the input for the following one (see figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8: Overview of the information extraction pipeline.

The pipeline takes as input a plain text document such as the one in figure 4.9 and returns as output a list of items like the one given in table 4.5. Each item consists of a label, a type – as defined in my annotation scheme (section 4.3.1) – and a unique identifier, expressed as a CTS URN, which links the item to the corresponding record in the knowledge base.

In this section I describe how I implemented each of the intermediate steps that are needed to transform a plain text into the desired output. I also touch upon the challenges that I faced during the development process, but this point is articulated more fully in section 4.5 where I discuss the evaluation of the information extraction pipeline.

²⁰ The code that I have written to implement this pipeline is available under an open access licence at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10886>.

Text of APh 75-06176 (named entities highlighted in bold)

Vergil has been appropriated for many different perspectives on the world. These appropriations involve assimilations that tend to erase the particularly Roman aspects of **Vergil**. It is important to make, or keep, Vergil strange, especially in the area of translation. A defamiliarizing reading of **Aen. 1,1-11** helps to illustrate how some English translations of the « **Aeneid** » map onto the spectrum of assimilation-dissimilation.

Figure 4.9: An example of the pipeline input: the text of APh 75-06176.

Table 4.5: An example of the pipeline output: for each named entity or relation contained in APh 75-06176 the table shows the corresponding string, the annotation type and the identifier that disambiguates it.

String	Type	Identifier (CTS URN)
Vergil	Aauthor	urn:cts:latinLit:phi0690
Vergil	Aauthor	urn:cts:latinLit:phi0690
Aen. 1,1-11	Scope	urn:cts:latinLit:phi0690.phi003:1.1-1.11
« Aeneid »	Awork	urn:cts:latinLit:phi0690.phi003

4.4.1 Pre-processing

The pre-processing phase entails a number of operations that are necessary in order to transform an unstructured stream of text into a more structured collection of sentences and tokens. Two examples of information that are added to the input text at this stage are the language in which a given text is written and the lexical syntactic category for each token in the text (i.e. `\gls{pos}` tag).

Language Identification

The grammatical categories – or PoS tags – that are assigned to a token vary depending on its language. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the language of a text first in order to extract the appropriate set of PoS tags for all the tokens it contains.

The language identification was performed by using `guess_language`²¹, a Python library that is able to recognise over 60 languages. The library uses the frequency of trigrams (i.e. sequences of three characters) in order to determine the language of the input text. Although the accuracy of this library was not the object of formal evaluation in this study, close

²¹ Guess-language 0.2, <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/guess-language>.

inspection of the results revealed that in the vast majority of cases the library's guess was accurate.

Sentence Segmentation

The main reason why texts are split into sentences when extracting canonical citations is that the co-occurrence of two or more citations within the same sentence may be an important indicator of their relatedness. In this sense, the sentence constitutes a unity of context that is granular enough to be meaningful, especially when the text is fairly long and contains many citations of primary sources such as in journal articles. In fact, it does make a difference to say that two citations are related because they occur within the same sentence as opposed to being found within the same article.

The automatic splitting of a text into sentences is usually a straightforward task. However, the high density of abbreviations that characterise publications in domains such as Classics constitute a challenge for many NLP tools that are available for this purpose.

When a tool does not have a robust enough way of handling abbreviations, the trailing dot of an abbreviation is mistakenly interpreted as a final stop signalling the end of a sentence. Since the sentence segmentation is typically performed at the beginning of a pipeline, an error at this stage may initiate a cascade of errors in the subsequent steps, thus leading to a drastic deterioration of the overall performance of the system.²²

The comparison of the different solutions that I have tested showed that the most reliable way of splitting a text containing a high number of abbreviations into sentences was to use the sentence segmentation script provided by Brat.²³ This fact, however, is hardly surprising given that Brat has been developed by the BioNLP community where biomedical texts like publications in Classics are characterised by an extensive use of abbreviations.

²² See *infra* p. 162 for an example of this phenomenon.

²³ The Python script `sencesplit.py` can be found at <https://github.com/nlplab/brat/blob/master/tools/sencesplit.py> and is based on the sentence splitter that was used to create the GENIA corpus, an annotated corpus of biomedical abstracts. The source code for the GENIA sentence splitter can be found at <https://github.com/ninjin/geniass/>.

Tokenisation and PoS Tagging

Tokenisation is the process of breaking up a stream of text into smaller chunks that are called tokens, while PoS tagging consists of assigning to each token the corresponding lexical syntactic category (e.g. verb, adverb, pronoun, etc.). As previously mentioned, the set of PoS tags varies depending on the language and for some languages like English several competing tagsets exist.

It is worth noting that tokens do not necessarily always correspond to words: for instance, when tokenising the string “influenced by Pliny, nat. 11, 4, 11 and 11, 16, 46 and” (see figure 4.6) each punctuation sign becomes a separate token. For this reason, and especially when referring to the size of the training set, it is more appropriate to refer to tokens rather than words as atomic units.

The main argument for extracting PoS tags is that they proved to be one of the most informative features for the extraction of named entities from text (Romanello, 2013, p. 13). To perform both the tokenisation and PoS tagging I used the tool *TreeTagger*²⁴, which is a probabilistic tool that supports a number of languages including English, French, German, Italian and Spanish (Schmid, 1994,9). Several interfaces to this tool have been written in different programming languages and I used one written in Python²⁵.

Abbreviations constituted a challenge for the text tokenisation as they did for the sentence segmentation. The string “nat.”, for example, would be erroneously split into two separate tokens: “nat” tagged as being a proper noun and “.” with PoS tag “SENT”, which stands for end punctuation. In order to overcome this issue, *TreeTagger* offers the possibility of specifying a list of abbreviations to use when tokenising a text. Since the most common abbreviations for author names and work titles are included in the `\gls{kb}`, a list of such abbreviations can easily be generated and passed to *TreeTagger*.

4.4.2 *Named Entity Extraction*

The extraction of named entities from text is the first real processing step after the preparatory steps that were just discussed (i.e. language

²⁴ *TreeTagger*, <http://www.cis.uni-muenchen.de/~schmid/tools/TreeTagger>.

²⁵ *treetagger-python*, <https://github.com/miotto/treetagger-python>.

detection, sentence segmentation, tokenisation and PoS tagging). The entities to be captured, as described in section 4.3.1, are *Aauthor*, *Awork*, *Refauwork* and *Refscope*. Various combinations of these four entities allow us to annotate virtually any kind of canonical citation, from the more concise and structured to the more discursive.

The approach that I have adopted to tackle this task is based on machine learning and specifically on supervised learning algorithms, meaning that the rules for the identification of these entities are not specified in advance but are extracted from a training set and learned by a statistical model.²⁶ Assigning named entity tags to tokens is decided by the model based on a set of features that is computed for each token (i.e. the feature vector). This section describes the feature set I have devised for the extraction of citations and other relevant named entities. In section 4.5.1 I compare the performance of different statistical models trained using the same feature set and the same training data.

Linguistic Features

Since the system was designed to be as language-independent as possible, the number of linguistic features to extract has been kept to a minimum as linguistic features are always language-dependent. First, the PoS tag as extracted by *TreeTagger* was included in the feature set without performing any manual correction. Second, the neighbouring words of each token w_i in the range $w_{i-2} \dots w_{i+2}$ were considered as features. Interestingly, experiments with using features such as word suffixes and prefixes of up to 4 characters in length in addition to the neighbouring tokens showed a degradation in the performance.

Word-level Features

Additional features were captured describing different aspects of the characters that form a token (e.g. punctuation, case, etc.). As the evaluation of the performance showed, this kind of features alone are responsible for a substantial improvement (i.e. +18.37%) of the overall accuracy of the system (Romanello, 2013, p. 13). These features are modelled after those proposed by Councill et al. (2008) for the extraction of modern bibliographic references and were designed specifically

²⁶ The algorithms that were used, as well as the reasons for choosing them, are presented in section 4.5.1.

to leverage the characteristics of canonical citations. For example, the punctuation and case features capture patterns of capitalisation as well as the presence of characters such as hyphens, quotation marks and brackets that are often found within or in conjunction with canonical citations (see tables 4.6 and 4.7).

Table 4.6: Named entity extraction: selected examples of punctuation features.

Feature Value	Example
final_dot	"georg."
continuing_punctuation	"," ","
quotation_mark	"«", "»"
has_hyphen	"61-73"
bracket	"(", "]"
no_punctuation	"view"

Table 4.7: Named entity extraction: selected examples of case features.

Feature Value	Example
mixed_caps	"georg."
all_caps	"BS"
init_caps	"Verg."
all_lower	"luogo"

Table 4.8: Named entity extraction: selected examples of number features.

Feature Value	Example
number	"322"
roman_number	"XI"
Year	"1900"
range	"13-19"
dot_separated_number	"5.1.10"
dot_separated_plus_range	"1.1-1.10"
mixed_alphanum	"12a"
no_digits	"those"

Moreover, a set of features was required to capture the characteristics of the Refscope entities – i.e. the entities that represent the scope of canonical citations. Such entities constitute approximately one-third of the total number of entities in the training set and are characterised primarily by the presence of numbers and punctuation signs. For these

reasons, the number feature covers a wide variety of aspects that are commonly found in the scope of citations (see table 4.8): a) the use of Roman numerals to indicate the book number of the cited work; b) the use of the hyphen for citations that refer to a range of text sections; c) the use of the dot “.” to distinguish the hierarchical levels of the cited work and d) the presence of a mixture of digits and letters that characterises citations adhering to specific citation schemes such as Bekker numbers or Stephanus.²⁷

Finally, the pattern feature aims to create relations between words that are not identical but that exhibit similar patterns concerning the sequence of characters (table 4.9). The first of these patterns, the so-called *extended pattern*, is computed by replacing lowercase characters with “a”, uppercase ones with “A”, numbers with “o” and punctuation signs with “-”. For example, the extended pattern of “Avien.”, which stands for Avienus, is “Aaaaa-” and is identical to the pattern of “Strab.”, which indicates the author Strabo. Additionally, a compressed pattern is extracted from each token by replacing sequences of similar characters with one single pattern character: “Aaaaa-” is compressed into “Aa-” and, as a result, the abbreviations “Avien.”, “Strab.” and “Thuc” (and many others) share the same compressed pattern (“Aa-”). These patterns aim to capture high-level similarity between strings.

Table 4.9: Named entity extraction: selected examples of pattern features.

Feature Value	Example
extended pattern	“Avien.” -> “Aaaaa-”
compressed pattern	“Avien.” -> “Aa-”

Semantic Features

Semantic features – or list lookup features – unlike the features that have been considered so far capture some aspects of the meaning of strings. Four different semantic features are extracted from each token and indicate whether or not the target token matches a pre-compiled list containing names, titles and abbreviations (see table 4.10). This list, often referred to as a dictionary or gazetteer, is drawn from the ontological knowledge base, as is the list of abbreviations used to improve the accuracy of tokenisation and sentence segmentation. The semantic

²⁷ For a discussion of these citation schemes see *infra* at p. 58.

features distinguish between words that partly match a name or title (e.g. “women” in “The catalog of women”) from words that produce a total match (e.g. “Aristofane” or “Theogony”). This distinction is particularly useful when handling author names or work titles that consist of more than one token.

Table 4.10: Named entity extraction: selected examples of semantic features.

Feature Value	Example
match_authors_dict	“Aristofane”
contained_authors_dict	“of”
match_works_dict	“Theogony”
contained_works_dict	“women”

At this point of the pipeline the language of the input text was automatically detected and the text itself split into sentences. In turn, each sentence was broken up into tokens that were automatically tagged with their lexical syntactic category and, finally, authors, works and other citation components were automatically identified.

4.4.3 Relation Detection

The next step to be performed is to detect the relations existing between named entities. As previously illustrated, the annotation scheme contains the scope relation which represents a citation as a relationship between two entities. The input is the text annotated with named entity information and the output is a list of relations, where each relation represents a canonical citation; in turn, each relation consists of a relation type (i.e. scope) and the named entities that are involved in the relation, which are also called the arguments of the relation. By definition, the second argument of the relation is always a Refscope entity, while the first argument can have type Aauthor, Awork or Refauwork. As a result, there are three possible combinations of named entities that can be part of a scope relation:

1. arg1=Aauthor, arg2=Refscope; e.g. “Ammianus (15, 8, 7)”;
2. arg1=Awork, arg2=Refscope; e.g. “Trabajos 159–173”;
3. arg1=Refauwork, arg2=Refscope; e.g. “Pliny, nat. 11, 4, 11”.

Rule-based Detection

To determine when a relation between any two named entities in a text exists I have devised a set of rules expressed by algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode for the FindRelations function

```

1: procedure FINDRELATIONS(entities)
2:   relations  $\leftarrow$  list()
3:   for all entity  $\in$  entities do
4:     if entity.type  $\neq$  "Refscope" then
5:       arg1  $\leftarrow$  entity
6:     else if entity.type = "Refscope" then
7:       if arg1  $\neq$  None then
8:         arg2  $\leftarrow$  entity
9:         relations  $\leftarrow$  list(arg1, arg2)
10:      end if
11:    end if
12:  end for
13:  return relations
14: end procedure

```

The design of the algorithm is based on the observation that the cited passage normally follows the mention of the cited author or work and is applied sequentially from left to right to all named entities in the input text (1.3). The relations are stored in a list, which is empty at the beginning of the procedure (1.2). Whenever an entity with type Aauthor, Awork or Refauwork is encountered (1.4) this entity is retained as a possible relation candidate and thus stored in the variable arg1 (1.5). If this variable already contains a previously found entity, its value is replaced with the current entity. Moreover, whenever a Refscope entity is found (1.6), the algorithm first checks if a relation candidate was already found (1.7): if this is the case, the current entity is assigned to the variable arg2 and a new relation is created and added to the list (1.9); otherwise, nothing happens and the algorithm moves on to the next entity.

Figure 4.10 illustrates how the algorithm works by representing schematically the status of a programme that implements this algorithm at four different execution steps, each of them corresponding to one iteration of the loop at the lines 1.4-1.12. At step 1 the entity being considered is "Ammianus": since its entity type is Aauthor (1.4), this entity is assigned to the variable arg1 (1.5) and the algorithm moves on the next entity. The steps 2 and 3 are identical to step 1, with the only difference

Figure 4.10: This diagram depicts the execution of the algorithm over four entities: the tokens occurring between these entities are not represented as the algorithm considers only named entities. The entity that is being processed at each step is indicated by a red arrow; on the right hand side the value of the variables before and after executing that step is provided.

that the value of variable `arg1` changes. When the algorithm reaches step 4, the variable `arg1` points to “Aen.”; since the entity type now in focus is `Refscope` (1.6) the entity is assigned to the variable `arg2` (1.8) and a new relation is created and added to the list of relations (1.9).

This algorithm enables the identification of relations that may extend across multiple sentences as well as consecutive citations that are constituted by non consecutive tokens (for an example see figure 4.4, p. 124). However, since this algorithm is designed to process the text from left to right, it is not suitable for capturing the more discursive citations such as “le livre 18 de la « Chronographia »” where the citation scope occurs before the reference to the cited work.²⁸

4.4.4 Entity and Relation Disambiguation

This step of the information extraction pipeline is directly concerned with the content or meaning of the pieces of information that are cap-

²⁸ For a discussion of the impact of this kind of citations on the evaluation results see *infra* p. 155.

tured. The goal of this step is to identify unambiguously each extracted entity mention and relation (i.e. citation) by means of a unique identifier.

The following example summarises what is the result of the extraction steps examined up to this point. The article entitled *Propertiana* that was published in 2004 by W. S. Watt in the journal *Rheinisches Museum für Philologie* is summarised by the APh abstract 75-04686, which reads as follows (named entities highlighted in bold):

Textkritisches zu **Propertz 1, 2, 9-14 ; 1, 18, 25-28 ; 2, 6, 31-32 ; 2, 25, 21-22 ; 2, 32, 23-24 ; 3, 7, 57-60 ; 3, 21, 31-32 und 4, 3, 7-10.**

Albeit concise, the abstract is highly informative as it allows the reader with an interest in textual criticism to know what specific passages of Propertius' *Elegiae* are debated in this article. After performing named entity extraction and relation detection on this text, a list of canonical citations is obtained and represented as relations between the various named entities that constitute the citation:

R1 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T2", "Refscope", "1, 2, 9-14 ;")
 R2 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T3", "Refscope", "1, 18, 25-28 ;")
 R3 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T4", "Refscope", "2, 6, 31-32 ;")
 R4 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T5", "Refscope", "2, 25, 21-22 ;")
 R5 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T6", "Refscope", "2, 32, 23-24 ;")
 R6 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T7", "Refscope", "3, 7, 57-60 ;")
 R7 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T8", "Refscope", "3, 21, 31-32")
 R8 Arg1: ("T1", "Refauwork", "Propertz") Arg2: ("T8", "Refscope", "4, 3, 7-10.")

The final step is to associate each citation with the corresponding unique identifier, expressing in a machine readable format which text passage is being cited. For example, the canonical reference "Propertz 1, 2, 9-14" – one of the *loci* addressed by Watt's article – needs to be transformed into the CTS URN urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:1.2.9-1.2.14. Applying this to the list above results in the following list of identifiers:

R1 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:1.2.9-1.2.14
 R2 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:1.18.25-1.18.28
 R3 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:2.6.31-2.6.32
 R4 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:2.25.21-2.25.22
 R5 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:2.32.23-2.32.24

R6 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:3.7.57-3.7.60
 R7 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:3.21.31-3.21.32
 R8 urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.phi001:4.3.7-4.3.10

The operation of transforming the human readable notation “Properz 1, 2, 9–14” of the example above into a machine actionable identifier entails two distinct sub-steps. First, it is necessary to determine that the string “Properz” is commonly used within the context of a citation as a shortcut to refer to the *Elegies*, identified by the URN urn:cts:latinLit:phi0620.-phi001. Second, it is necessary to map the citation scope “1, 2, 9–14” – which translates to “book 1, poem 2, lines 9 to 14” – to the normalised form “1.2.9–1.2.14”. In such a normalised form compressed ranges of passages are expanded and hierarchical levels of the cited work are dot-separated.

Assigning each citation the correspondent unique identifier requires a substantial amount of information that is not contained in or can be deduced from the text. This sort of information is contained in the knowledge base about the domain of Classics discussed in chapter 3. This knowledge base plays the most central role in the disambiguation step as it holds information such as unique identifiers, name or title variants and information about the *opus maximum* of a given author.

Matching Entities against the Knowledge-Base

Generally speaking, matching the extracted Aauthor and Awork entities against the knowledge base consists of looking up the string to match in a set of dictionaries. These dictionaries, as already mentioned, consist of abbreviations and variants of names of ancient authors and titles of works. Some clean-up and normalisation is performed on the search string prior to the lookup: punctuation signs that may surround or be included in the extracted named entity are removed and the string is transformed to lowercase in order to facilitate the matching. Similarly, all names and titles are turned to lowercase when constructing the dictionaries; additionally, articles that are present within work titles are removed (e.g. *The Acharnians* becomes “acharnians”). Without removing the articles from the titles, a lookup of “Acharnians” would return no exact matches as the normative titles contained in the knowledge base always comprise the determinative article.

Matching Refauwork entities is slightly more complicated as this entity type captures strings that need to be treated in different ways. Strings

like “Pliny, nat.”, “Georg.” or “Thuc.” are all labelled by the system as Refauwork. As a result, it is necessary to apply a set of heuristics when matching entities of this kind in order to determine the dictionary in which the string should be looked up. First, the programme assumes that the string is a title (or the abbreviation of a title) and tries to match it against the dictionary of titles. If no matches are found, the programme looks up the string against the dictionary of author names. Finally, if the second attempt does not succeed and provided that the string contains more than one word, the programme tries to split it and look up the words that constitute the string in separate dictionaries.

So far I have talked about *matching* without further specifying what type of matching is being performed. Matching of two strings can either be exact or approximate: *exact matching* means that two strings match when they are identical, whereas *approximate matching* matches strings that are similar. The similarity between strings can be quantified by using several metrics. The metric I used in my research is known as Levenshtein distance or simply as *edit distance* and measures the dissimilarity between two strings in terms of operations – i.e. insertions, deletions and substitutions – that need to be performed in order to transform one string into the other. For example, the string “Vergil” and “Virgilio” have an edit distance of 3: in fact, to transform the former into the latter one needs to substitute “e” with “i”, insert an “i” after “Virgil” and append an “o” at the end. Since each of these operations has a cost of 1, the distance equals the sum of the costs, i.e. 3.

When performing approximate matching it is useful to specify a threshold so that matching candidates with an edit distance that exceeds such a threshold can be discarded. This type of matching, as opposed to exact matching, may be a desirable approach when trying to match a string that may be wrongly transcribed, for instance due to OCR errors. In the specific case of matching names and titles, approximate matching within a certain threshold proved to be a viable solution for me given the nature of the data I have been dealing with. In fact, variants in different languages of the name of an ancient author tend to have a relatively low edit distance as they generally stem from the Latin or Greek name (e.g. “Homer”, “Homère”, “Homerus” and “Omero”). Therefore, this approach is useful when the string to be matched is not contained

in the knowledge base but partly matches against other author names contained in it.²⁹

Normalisation of Citation Scope

The final step of the pipeline is to normalise the part of a canonical citation that indicates which specific part of a given text is being cited, the so-called *citation scope*. Since the same scope may be indicated by means of several equivalent representations it becomes necessary to map all such variants to a common normalised form in order to minimise variation and ambiguity. For example, a reference to Thucydide's *Histories* book 1, chapter 89, sections 1–2 may be written as:

1. Thuc. 1.89.1–2
2. Thuc. 1, 89, 1–2
3. Thuc. I 89, 1s.

Transforming these human-readable notations into a computationally tractable representation requires absolute explicitness and consistency (see section 3.1). Therefore, the citation scope needs to be mapped onto a normalised representation, in this case “1.89.1–1.89.2”. The human reader, however, will interpret these three notations in the same way, despite the fact that they are expressed in slightly different ways. The first two citations differ only by the punctuation symbol used to separate the hierarchical levels of the cited work (i.e. book/chapter/section) respectively the dot “.” in the former and the colon “;” in the latter. The third citation uses the Latin ordinal number to indicate the book and the abbreviation “s.” – which in Italian and French stands respectively for *segunte* and *suivant* (i.e. “following”) – to refer to the following section. Moreover, when the citation scope consists of a range of passages some details may be left implicit to avoid repetitions, thus leaving to the reader the task of figuring out the omitted pieces of information. In the examples above, for instance, the range of passages may be expressed as “1.89.1–2”, instead of the more verbose form “1.89.1–1.89.2”, because the cited sections are both found in the same book and chapter.

²⁹ In my research I have experimented with both exact and approximate matching. In section 4.5.3 I discuss the respective drawbacks and advantages of using these two approaches.

The technique I have used in order to process and normalise the citation scopes is called *parsing*, and specifically parsing based on Context-free Grammar (CFG). As part of my research I built a parser that follows a set of rules specified as a CFG in order to extract some structure from citation scopes.

A good example of the purposes for which CFGs are widely employed is the compiling of programming languages, namely the transformation of code into a set of low-level instructions that can be executed by the machine. Each programming language has its syntactic rules that any code written in that language must follow and these rules can be expressed by means of a CFG. By relying on these rules, the compiler can check if any piece of code is well-formed or, in other words, if all the syntactic rules of the language in which the code is written are followed correctly. Typically, a compiler uses a parser in order to process the code being compiled and in doing so relies on a grammar of rules that describe the syntax of that specific language.

CFGs can be used to parse specific kinds of strings such as patent numbers or citation scopes because they resemble closely a formal notation that follows a finite set of rules. Recently, CFGs have been successfully applied to the processing of specific sections of scholarly publications in Classics such as indexes and critical apparatuses, which follow a relatively rigid structure. Boschetti (2007), for example, has applied CFG-based parsing to critical apparatuses based on the observation that their structure is suitable for formalisation by means of a grammar.³⁰ Similarly, I have demonstrated elsewhere that parsing can be successfully applied to capture the structure of indexes of cited passages that can be found at the end of scholarly publications (Romanello et al., 2009a).

The framework I have used to implement the parser is called ANother Tool for Language Recognition (ANTLR)³¹, which is an open source framework for building parsers (Parr and Quong, 1995). Although ANTLR is mostly used to build grammars for the parsing of programming languages, it has also been applied to NLP problems such as for example the extraction of patent numbers from legal texts (Surdeanu et al., 2014).

³⁰ The critical apparatus is the section of a critical edition where the editor records variant readings and conjectures about the text and where references backing the editor's choices in establishing the text are provided.

³¹ ANTLR, <http://www.antlr.org/>.

Figure 4.11: Schematic representation of the lexer grammar rules that are matched when tokenising the string “Thuc. 1.89.1-2;”; each token is coloured according to the rule it satisfies.

Since providing a detailed explanation of how the parser was implemented and how CFGs work falls outside the scope of this dissertation, I shall attempt to illustrate the underlying idea by describing how the citation “Thuc. 1.89.1-2;” can be parsed by using a CFG-based parser (figures 4.11 to 4.13).

First of all, the ANTLR parser consists of three components: a lexer, a parser and a tree parser. Each of these components is described by a grammar of rules which are usually applied sequentially. The lexer grammar defines a set of rules for splitting the text stream into a sequence of smaller blocks, the tokens. Figure 4.11 shows schematically the set of tokenisation rules that was defined and the result once they are applied to the string “Thuc. 1.89.1-2;”. A character, represented by the token CHAR, is defined as any character in the range “a-z” and “A-Z”. Token rules can also be combined to form more complex building blocks: the token LITERAL, for example, is defined as (CHAR+ PUNCT* CHAR*), which means a sequence of one or more characters that may contain also one or more punctuation signs (e.g. “Thuc.”).

The stream of tokens that is outputted by the lexer becomes the input for the parser (figure 4.12). The parser rules describe in a recursive way which sequences of tokens are expected, and thus accepted, by the parser. The top-level rule ((ref (ref_separator ref)*)) says that the input string is a sequence of one or more references separated by a semicolon. A reference, identified by the rule ref: work* scope, is

PARSER GRAMMAR RULES

```

input: (ref (ref_separator ref)*)
ref: work* scope
work : (LITERAL+)
scope: (scope_single | scope_range);

scope_range: (level HYPHEN level)
level: INT (lev_sep INT)*
lev_sep:(COMMA | DOT);

```

Figure 4.12: Schematic representation of how the stream of tokens representing the string “Thuc. 1.89.1-2;” is parsed according to a set of grammar rules (only the rules that are matched are displayed).

further defined as a sequence of work and scope elements; the work element may be omitted, as indicated by the star “*” symbol, meaning that both “Thuc. 1.89.1-2;” and “1.89.1-2;” are valid inputs for this parser. The grammar rules continue with more fine-grained rules such as level and lev_sep.

The output of this parser is a parse tree, namely a tree structure that represents the hierarchy of elements that are produced by a grammar of rules (see figure 4.13a). Such a parse tree can then be traversed by using a tree parser and transformed into a data structure such as the fragment of JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) depicted in figure 4.13b. While traversing the tree some operations are performed such as making fully explicit the compressed notation used to refer to contiguous passages of text (e.g. “1.89.1-2” is transformed into “1.89.1-1.89.2”).

4.5 EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE

An important aspect of automating the extraction of canonical citations is the ability to measure the accuracy with which the task is carried out. In this case the accuracy refers to how many citations were correctly identified and how many were missed. In this section I present an evaluation of the system to extract such references described in the previous

Figure 4.13: This figure shows a) the parse tree resulting from parsing the string "Thuc. 1.89.1-2;" and b) a JSON representation of the parse tree after normalising the range of cited passages.

section. The three steps that make up the evaluation process will now be considered separately:

1. **The extraction of named entities:** the identification of names, titles and references in the text;
2. **The detection of the relations that exist between entities:** since a reference is represented as a relation between two entities, the canonical references are reconstructed starting from the entities that are found in the text;
3. **The disambiguation of named entities and relations:** the system tries to determine which entity, from those that are contained in the knowledge base, is referred to in the text; in order to do so each entity and relation is assigned a unique identifier, a CTS URN.

The kind of evaluation to be carried out depends on the nature of the solution being evaluated. When evaluating machine learning-based solutions it is necessary to keep separate the training and the test set. For

the evaluation to be meaningful, the data that was used to train the system must not be used in the evaluation. Obviously, this necessity does not apply to the evaluation of rule-based algorithms as the classification rules are defined a priori and are not derived from observations on the data.

Among the methods that are used in statistics for evaluation purposes I have employed the *k-fold cross-validation*, specifically the 10-fold cross-validation, a method that is commonly used for the evaluation of NLP systems. A key concept of cross-validation is that the dataset is divided into k subsets and the evaluation is performed on each subset in successive *rounds*. To perform a 10-fold cross-validation the dataset is divided into 10 subsets: at round 1, the first subset is used for training and the remaining (9) subsets are used for evaluation, i.e. to compute precision, recall and F_1 score. This procedure is repeated for the remaining subsets and the evaluation results are then averaged over the rounds.³²

The data used for the evaluation was drawn solely from the APh corpus (section 4.3.2) as it was the only one to be manually corrected. The metrics that are used to assess the performances of the system – precision, recall and F_1 score – were introduced in section 4.5.

It is worth noting that one limit of this evaluation is the lack of an already existing baseline with which the results can be compared. To overcome this limitation, which is due to the innovative nature of my research, I have compared the results of using different solutions to perform the same task (e.g. the use of different statistical models for the extraction of named entities).

4.5.1 *Evaluation of Named Entity Extraction*

The first step in extracting canonical references from text is the automatic identification of author names, work titles and references to specific work passages as these entities constitute the building blocks of such references. These blocks are mapped onto named entities – i.e. *Author*, *Awork*, *Refauwork* and *Refscope* – as was described in section 4.3.1. Since an entity may consist of multiple tokens (e.g. the title “Works and Days”), each entity is in fact represented by two distinct tags: the first

³² It should also be noted that the implementation of 10-fold cross-validation that I have used balances the number of positive and negative instances that are contained in each subset.

token of an entity is tagged with the name of the entity itself to which the prefix B-, which stands for beginning, is appended; for all the following tokens the prefix I- is used.³³ For example, the title *Works and Days* is represented as:

B-AWORK/Works I-AWORK/and I-AWORK/Days

As a result, extracting named entities is the task of classifying a sequence of tokens by assigning to each token one of the following tags: B-AUTHOR, I-AUTHOR, B-AWORK, I-AWORK, B-REFAUWORK, I-REFAUWORK, B-REFSCOPE, I-REFSCOPE or the tag 0 if the token does not constitute a named entity.

What was evaluated is how well different machine learning algorithms perform the task of extracting named entities from text. The dataset that was employed for the 10-fold cross-evaluation contains in total 25,889 tokens and 1,261 named entities. The performances are assessed based on the standard measures of precision, recall and F_1 score. However, one distinction needs to be made concerning how these measures were computed. I did consider the number of correct *tags* whereas in other contexts, such as the CoNLL shared task, the calculation is based on the number of correct *entities*. The difference between the two approaches is that if the system outputs the sequence 0/I-AWORK/I-AWORK instead of B-AWORK/I-AWORK/I-AWORK this counts as two true positives and one false negative, instead of considering the entire entity as not correctly recognised.

Three machine learning algorithms have been evaluated on this task: Conditional Random Fields (CRF), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt).³⁴ These algorithms are commonly applied to the task of NER as well as to other tasks. The CRF model, which was theorised by Lafferty et al. (2001), has been applied to a wide range of classification problems including computer vision and bioinformatics and is currently considered the state-of-the-art method in sequence labeling tasks such as NER.³⁵ The SVM was theorised by Vapnik (1995) and ever since has been successfully and widely used in text classification and sequence labelling applications, including NER

³³ This file format was explained in section 4.3.3.

³⁴ In writing this section I have used as references Jurafsky and Martin (2009), Manning et al. (2008) and Hastie et al. (2009).

³⁵ For an introduction to CRF and its possible applications see Sutton and McCallum (2006).

(see e.g. Mayfield et al., 2003). Finally MaxEnt, also called Multinomial Logistic Regression model, has been applied since the 1990s to many supervised problems in NLP such as for example sentence-boundary detection and machine translation. Applications of MaxEnt to NER are e.g. Borthwick et al. (1998) and Chieu and Ng (2003).

Discussing in detail the foundations of these algorithms falls outside the scope of this dissertation as it would require introducing a number of very technical concepts from mathematics and statistics. However, it is worth making a few general remarks concerning the nature of these algorithms.

First, CRF, SVM and MaxEnt are all supervised learning algorithms in the sense that they take as input labelled data and use the input to predict the value of the outputs, yet they use different methods to predict the output. Two of the chosen algorithms – CRF and MaxEnt – are probabilistic in that the decision of which class label needs to be assigned to a given token is based on the probability of assigning that class given the observed features. SVM, on the other hand, represents each instance as a multidimensional vector of features and uses the vector space to classify such instances.³⁶

Second, only CRF is optimised for labelling sequences of items rather than single instances, what in machine learning terms is called the prediction of structured outputs. There are two possible solutions to obviate this issue so that the comparison between different algorithms remains meaningful. The first solution is to use combinations of these algorithms with Hidden Markov Models (HMM), such as SVM^{hmm} and MaxEnt Markov Models, which are optimised for sequence labelling tasks. The second solution – the one I have adopted here – is to employ a sliding-window labeller which allows the classifier to take into account the features assigned to the preceding and following tokens within a window of a certain size for training and classification purposes (in this specific case, the two preceding and two following tokens are considered).

The evaluation results I shall present next were produced by using existing implementations of these three algorithms, specifically a C++ implementation of CRF, called CRF++³⁷ and the SVM and MaxEnt imple-

³⁶ For a detailed description of the feature set see section 4.4.2.

³⁷ I have used version 0.15.2 of the scikit-learn library and version 0.55 of CRF++.

mentations that are provided by scikit-learn³⁸ (Pedregosa et al., 2011), a machine learning library written in Python. Moreover, the statistical models were employed without modifying the default values of the parameters that each model implementation provides.³⁹

The CRF method produced the best overall results with overall F1-score, precision and recall respectively of 73.88%, 79.24% and 69.62% (see table 4.11). All three algorithms produced relatively similar results: CRF performed slightly better than SVM (+1.95%) and moderately better than MaxEnt (+3.45%). The breakdown of the evaluation results by entity type reflects a very similar situation (table 4.12). CRF outperforms the other models with regards to the extraction of two entities out of four (i.e. Awork and Refauwork), while SVM yields the best results for the two remaining entity types (i.e. Aauthor and Refscope).

Table 4.11: Evaluation results for the named entity extraction: overall precision, recall and F₁ score of CRF, MaxEnt and SVM.

Algorithm	Precision	Recall	F ₁ Score
CRF	79.24%	69.62%	73.88%
MaxEnt	75.29 %	66.75%	70.43%
SVM	74.44%	70.21%	71.93%

Remarkably, the accuracy with which the names of ancient authors are extracted (i.e. F₁ score of Aauthor entities) is much lower than the rest of the entities across all three models, with a resulting negative effect on the overall accuracy. More precisely, all models fail to capture a high number of author names, as the lower values of recall indicate. Looking more closely at the errors, it is possible to observe that author names tend to be missed more often when they do not occur in proximity to a work title or a canonical reference, and this also happens when the author name is exactly the same. One possible solution to the low recall of aauthor entities would be to extract some additional features that can help capture what characterises author names as opposed to words that are not proper names.

³⁸ Scikit-learn, <http://scikit-learn.org/>.

³⁹ I have used version 0.15.2 of the scikit-learn library and version 0.55 of CRF++.

Table 4.12: Evaluation results for the named entity extraction: precision, recall and F_1 score of CRF, MaxEnt and SVM, divided by named entity type.

Entity	CRF			SVM			MaxEnt		
	Prec	Rec	F_1	Prec	Rec	F_1	Prec	Rec	F_1
Aauthor	91.15%	39.67%	54.53%	86.51%	43.61%	57.79%	90.07%	36.96%	52.13%
Awork	96.54%	71.04%	81.60%	96.00%	69.33%	80.23%	95.71%	66.55%	78.14%
Refauwork	91.72%	76.56%	83.19%	86.70%	71.53%	78.04%	84.80%	64.81%	73.16%
Refscope	96.24%	77.65%	85.48%	94.59%	80.20%	86.60%	95.55%	78.23%	85.83%

4.5.2 Evaluation of Relation Detection

As illustrated in section 4.3.1, citations are represented in the annotated datasets as *binary relations* between named entities. Such relations are binary meaning that exactly two entities are involved in any relation; each of the entities involved is called an *argument* of that relation. In the annotation environment that was used, Brat, each relation is represented visually as an arrow connecting its two arguments (see figure 4.14).

Figure 4.14: Example of scope relations represented as binary relations between named entities and visualised in Brat.

The object of the evaluation presented in this section was the rule-based algorithm for the automatic detection of scope relations that was described above (see algorithm 1). The accuracy of this algorithm was evaluated based on the 381 relations contained in the 366 documents of the manually corrected dataset. The achieved precision, recall and F_1 score are respectively 93.33%, 91.87% and 92.60% (table 4.13). Given the fairly simple set of rules used by the algorithm – which currently uses as the sole criterion to detect relations the order in which entities appear in the text – the automatic detection of relations did not prove to be a particularly problematic processing step. The algorithm failed to detect approximately 8% of the total relations as indicated by the number of false negatives. Similarly, 6.5% of the extracted relations are erroneous

meaning that they were captured by the algorithm although they were not contained in the manually corrected data (i.e. false positives).

Table 4.13: Evaluation results for the relation detection: precision, recall and F_1 score of the rule-based algorithm.

True Pos	False Pos	False Neg	Precision	Recall	F_1 Score
350	25	31	93.33%	91.87%	92.60%

Looking at the actual mistakes made by the algorithm, and specifically at the missed relations, it is possible to observe that, as had already been anticipated, they are a relatively small number of cases where the relation proceeds from right to left instead of the relatively more common left-to-right order. The direction of the relation is determined by the order in which its arguments appear: left-to-right when the Refscope entity comes first and right-to-left when an entity of a different type comes first as happens in the vast majority of cases. A left-to-right scope relation characterises citations that are expressed in a discursive way: the reference “les v. 9–12 des « Acharniens »”, for example, can also be expressed in a more concise and less discursive way as “Ar. Ach. 9–12”. Some examples of the kind of relations that were missed by the algorithm are provided in table 4.14.

Table 4.14: Some examples of the relations that result from discursive citations.

Example	Relation	Example with POS Tags
du [REFSCOPE chant 4] de l’ [AWORK « Énéide »]	scope(“« Énéide »”, “chant 4”)	[PRP:det du]/[NOM chant]/[NUM 4]/[PRP de]/[DET:ART l’]/[PUN:cit «]/[NOM Énéide]/[PUN:cit »]
Le [REFSCOPE livre 13] de la [AWORK « Chronique »]	scope(“« Chronique »”, “livre 13”)	[DET:ART le]/[NOM livre]/[NUM 13]/[PRP de]/[DET:ART la]/[PUN:cit «]/[ADJ Chronique]/[PUN:cit »]
les [REFSCOPE v. 9–12] des [AWORK « Acharniens »]	scope(“« Acharniens »”, “v. 9–12”)	[DET:ART les]/[ABR v.]/[NUM 9–12]/[PRP:det des]/[PUN:cit «]/[NOM Acharniens]/[PUN:cit »]

One way of capturing such relations would be to add to the algorithm a rule that parses entities in a right-to-left order. Another solution, perhaps more robust, would be to employ a supervised learning approach and harness the common pattern of PoS tags that characterises these

relations. The sequence of PoS tags could be one of the features that are used to train a statistical model to detect relations from text.⁴⁰

4.5.3 *Evaluation of Entity and Relation Disambiguation*

Similar to the evaluation presented in the previous section, evaluating the disambiguation of entities and relations did not require a cross-evaluation strategy. In fact, the solution being evaluated did not involve any machine learning algorithm (section 4.4.4).

What was evaluated is the disambiguation of names of ancient authors (i.e. *Aauthor* entities), titles of their works (i.e. *Awork* entities) and references to specific sections of these works (i.e. *scope* relations). Approximately 55% of the 855 disambiguations contained in the training set concern authors and works, while the remaining 45% are disambiguations of canonical references. As was described above, the disambiguation of such references as well as of the mentions of authors and works is done by assigning the corresponding CTS URN to the entity that is being referred to.

Before considering the results in detail, it is worth highlighting that disambiguation is the processing step in which having an exhaustive knowledge base matters the most. Since an essential part of the disambiguation process consists of trying to match strings extracted from the text against lists of names, titles and abbreviations, the more complete such lists are the more accurate the matching is going to be. However, as I shall clarify later in the section, a more accurate matching does not necessarily guarantee better overall performances. In fact, to disambiguate correctly references that are ambiguous (i.e. they may be matched exactly but they refer to several entities) string matching needs to be complemented with ways of modelling the context where the string occurs.

Both exact and approximate matching to disambiguate entities and relations were evaluated as summarised in table 4.15.⁴¹ Two different threshold values were employed to measure the similarity between strings by means of edit distance (i.e. $n = 4$ and $n = 7$). Using a threshold value of 4, for example, means that matches with an edit distance

⁴⁰ For an overview of features that can be used to perform relation detection in a supervised machine learning setting see Jurafsky and Martin (2009, pp. 768–772).

⁴¹ For an explanation of the difference between exact and approximate matching see section 4.4.4.

greater than 4 are discarded. Increasing the threshold is particularly useful to match those names or titles that are not yet contained in the knowledge base and, in general, proves to be more useful for longer strings, such as work titles consisting of several words. The effects of using a different threshold are reflected in the results and specifically in the recall.

Table 4.15: Evaluation results for the disambiguation of aauthor and awork entities and scope relations.

Matching Type	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Exact	58.33%	62.88%	60.52%
Approximate (threshold=4)	61.04%	90.94%	73.05%
Approximate (threshold=7)	58.94%	94.76%	72.67%

The best performances were achieved by using approximate string matching with a threshold of 4: this led to an improvement of +12.53% over the exact matching and was not outperformed by using a higher threshold. The highest recall (94.76%) was achieved with a threshold value of 7, meaning the system can disambiguate some references that would otherwise have been missed. However, this higher recall came at the price of a lower precision (58.94%): in some cases it is correct that no match is found in the knowledge base. With a higher threshold the system also tended to find a match for those entities that should not have one. For instance, the reference « Lettera ai Romani » (i.e. *Epistle to the Romans*) is correctly interpreted by the system as being a reference to an ancient work (i.e. Awork entity) but this work is not contained in the knowledge base as it falls outside the scope of classical works. However, using approximate string matching with a threshold of 7 leads to additional but unrelated matches like “lettera ad erodoto”, “lettere di contadini” and “lettera di barnaba”.

What is remarkable about the results shown in table 4.15 is the relatively low precision of the system in comparison with the recall. In roughly 40% of the cases the system makes an incorrect guess concerning how a given entity or relation should be disambiguated, as the number of true positives and false positives shows. In order to identify the reason for such a low precision, it is useful to distinguish between the disambiguation of entities and the disambiguation of relations. As can be seen in table 4.16, excluding the relations from the evaluation leads to better results and to a levelling of precision and recall. This indicates

that the system fails in determining the right disambiguation for scope relations (i.e. citations) more often than when disambiguating entities.

Table 4.16: Evaluation results for the disambiguation of aauthor and awork entities only.

Matching Type	Precision	Recall	F ₁ Score
Exact	92.28%	54.56%	68.58%
Approximate (threshold=4)	82.42%	88.44%	85.32%
Approximate (threshold=7)	79.04%	93.32%	85.58%

In the results presented so far the the disambiguation of relations has emerged a particularly problematic task. At this point, it is worth recalling how the disambiguation works in the current implementation. Consider for example the citation “Thuc. I 89, 1s.”, which is represented as a relation of type scope between two entities. The first step is to determine which work is referred to by the string “Thuc.”, which corresponds to a Refauwork entity; the second step is to normalise the notation “I 89, 1s.”, which is the scope of the reference and is therefore captured by a Refscope entity, into “1.89.1–1.90.1”.

The first type of error committed by the system specifically concerns abbreviations. Consider the following example:

But **Horace** undermines the suggestion that his own poetry will forever represent the Augustan Age. **Carm.** 4, 15 in fact [...]

The system fails to determine that the abbreviation “Carm.” refers to the *Carmina* by Horace. The right choice here would probably be obvious to the reader: the name of Horace, which has been mentioned in the previous sentence, provides the *context* necessary to know that “Carm.” refers his *Carmina*. Unlike the human reader, the program – at least in its current implementation – attempts to disambiguate the abbreviation “Carm.” without relating it to the named entities contained in the previous or following sentences. As a result, a lookup of the string “Carm.” returns 75 exact matches (i.e. matches with edit distance equal to zero). As for the system all such matches are equally plausible, the first one is picked thus leading to an incorrect disambiguation.

Similar errors are committed by the system when highly ambiguous abbreviations such as “ann.” and “ep.” are encountered; these abbreviations, which stand respectively for *Annales* and *Epistulae*, similarly to

“carm.” can refer to several works and require us to consider the surrounding context in order to be correctly disambiguated (see table 4.17). One relatively straightforward way of avoiding similar errors would be to let the system take into account the preceding named entities when disambiguating a given abbreviation.

Table 4.17: The 10 most ambiguous abbreviations of ancient works in the knowledge base. The ambiguity of an abbreviation is measured based on the number of unique works it may refer to.

Abbreviation	Meaning	Unique Works
“epigr.”	Epigrammata	96
“carm.”	Carmina	75
“ep.”	Epistulae	74
“or.”	Orationes	73
“orat.”	Orationes	71
“epist.”	Epistulae	66
“hist.”	Historiae	37
“gramm.”	Grammatica	36
“ann.”	Annales	16

The second type of error committed by the system concerns ambiguous author names. The mention “Aristophanes”, for example, may refer to the comic playwright as well as to the Alexandrian grammarian Aristophanes of Byzantium. Similarly, “Pliny” may refer to Pliny the Younger or Pliny the Elder. Again, the method of ascertaining which of the possible entities is actually being referred to is to look at the surrounding context. Consider the following passage drawn from the beginning of the review of an article entitled *I grammatici alessandrini nei papiri di Aristofane*:

Esame dell’ esegesi papiracea ad **Aristofane** : permanenza del lavoro degli eruditi alessandrini [...]

Keywords such as “grammatici”, “eruditi”, “alessandrini”, “marginalia”, “hypomnemata”, “commentari”, “tardo-alessandrini”, which are contained both in the title and in the review, leave no doubt to the reader about the fact that the Aristophanes referred to in this context is Aristophanes of Byzantium.

Enabling the system to perform a similar operation – i.e. disambiguating a name based on words that occur in the surrounding text – would require us to make use of the *context*. In fact, the effect of the context in

natural language communication is to constrain interpretation or, in this case, to allow us to understand a reference despite its apparent ambiguity. However, as Hirst (1997) convincingly argued, creating a formal model of context is impossible as context is always constructed by the speaker (or author) and the interpreter. Therefore, given the impossibility of modelling the context, it is just possible to create something that approximates it, a surrogate.

One possible way of mimicking to some extent how context works would be to build for each entity in the knowledge base a list of co-occurring words. In order to extract words that are distinctive it is possible to remove the so-called *stopwords* first and then to retain only words that have a relatively low frequency within the training dataset. Moreover, in order to allow for multilingualism, one list of related words for each language is required; alternatively, one could maintain such a list in one language and then use language alignment to compare sequences of words written in other languages with this list.

The third type of error consists of a limited number of cases where the information necessary to disambiguate a citation is not contained in the text of the review but in the title of the reviewed publication. Since the title of the reviewed publication is by design not included in the dataset as is part of the metadata, such errors highlighted a limitation related to how the datasets have been constructed. An example of this type of error can be seen in the following passage:

Dans son **chap. 5** sur le squelette et la respiration, **Lactance** utilise des sources disparates et arrive aux limites de son savoir médical.

Without looking at the title of the article – “Lactance, *De opificio Dei* (303–304): le savoir médical au début du IV^e siècle” – it is not possible to guess to which of Lactantius’ works does the reference to chapter 5 refer.

The final error type concerns references that were expressed ambiguously. In such cases, which proved to be challenging not only for the programme but also for the human annotators, determining the correct answer is not always possible and when it is possible requires some additional knowledge about the cited works. Consider for instance the following passage:

Analysis of the pederastic poems in the Theocritean corpus (12 ; 23 ; 29 ; 30) reveals that **Theocritus** reflects on mutuality in a relationship [...]

Since two collections of poems are attributed to Theocritus – the *Idylls* and the *Epigrams* – the expression “pederastic poems” could equally refer to either of them. The human reader, however, will know – or at least is expected to know in this example – that this passage cannot refer to the *Epigrams* as only 22 epigrams are attributed to Theocritus. As this example shows, rhetorical choices with regards to how references are expressed made by the author make the task of automatically capturing such references considerably more challenging. In order to cope with such references it is necessary to build into the system some sort of reasoning capabilities that uses the data contained in the knowledge base: in the example below, the system could rule out the *Epigrams* after having checked that the references “29” and “30” are only valid in relation to the *Idylls*.

4.6 DISCUSSION AND FURTHER WORK

The results of the evaluation show that named entity extraction does provide a suitable framework to *translate* the extraction of canonical citations into a computationally tractable problem. This is what motivated my research in the first place. The evaluation results should be considered in light of the main research goal, which was to test *if, how* and *how well* the task of identifying, extracting and indexing canonical citations can be automated and not to create a programme that would achieve the best possible results in terms of accuracy in performing such task. As observed above, a limitation of the evaluation is that it was not possible to compare the performance of the system with a baseline due to the lack of comparable systems.

The importance and value for classicists of having a system to extract citations from text automatically has already been explained. One might ask, however, what the relevance is for a broader audience and more generally what contribution is being made to the field of NLP. I argue that performing citation extraction as a pre-processing step allows for greater accuracy in carrying out virtually any NLP task on texts coming from the domain of Classics. Indeed, abbreviations, which are exten-

signs is made within the reference and c) sufficient information concerning the cited text is contained in the knowledge base. That being said, substantial room for improvement exists to enhance the accuracy with which the extraction of canonical citations can be performed as I shall discuss next.

The first area of improvement is the population of the knowledge base with data about how to refer to classical texts as several processing tasks – i.e. sentence segmentation, text tokenisation, named entity recognition as well as disambiguation – can benefit, to a varying extent, from a more comprehensive knowledge base.

The second area of improvement concerns the application of machine learning algorithms to each of the three steps of citation extraction. In the current implementation of the system, the only step to which a machine learning-based approach has been applied is the recognition and classification of named entities. However, applying machine learning to the two remaining steps is not only possible but also desirable and interesting in itself insofar as it would allow us to compare such an approach with the rule-based approach that I have adopted.

Moreover, the accuracy of the named entity extraction can be improved in at least two respects. First, the number of features that are observed for each token can be increased by introducing new features. In addition to this, it is possible to select those features that prove to be most effective to learn the statistical model, the so-called *feature selection*. Second, the statistical models can be fine tuned by setting the parameters of each statistical model to different values in order to find the optimal combination of parameter settings.

The third (and last) area of improvement is related to expanding the training set, a task that overlaps substantially with continuing to grow the knowledge base. As new data is manually corrected and included into the training set, new pieces of information are found that can be fed back into the knowledge base by means of largely automated processes. Training data, in turn, could be expanded with regards to both its breadth and depth.

Expanding the breadth of the training set means to increase its size while trying to cover as many styles of citing primary sources as possible. The use of angle quotes to cite titles of ancient works (e.g. “Homer’s « Iliad »”), which is consistent throughout the APh, is a good example of a convention that is not common in every journal or publication in

Classics. Therefore, in order for the training set to be generalisable – i.e. suitable to support the extraction of canonical citations no matter the citation style they follow – the range of citation styles that are represented in the corpus needs to be as comprehensive as possible.

Expanding the depth of the training set involves extending the annotation scheme. As pointed out above, the accuracy with which the named entity classification is performed could be improved by introducing new types of named entities. These new entities would be especially useful to distinguish those strings that are most often confused with canonical references due to their surface similarity (e.g. references to papyri, citations of fragmentary texts, etc.). In addition to introducing new entities, the depth could be extended by adding new layers of linguistic annotations such as chunking and syntactic annotation. These additional layers of annotation can then be harnessed by using them as features while training a statistical model to learn the classification of named entities or the detection of relation between entities.

Moreover, adding the layer of syntactic annotations would allow us to capture the indication of the specific phenomenon about which a given text passage is cited. Consider the following sentence:

Ammianus' conception of how to deal with foreigners is based on Vergil's formulation of Rome's mission (Aen. 6, 851-853).

The syntactic parsing of this sentence allows us to identify the noun phrase "Vergil's formulation of Rome's mission" and to establish that the canonical reference given in brackets "(Aen. 6, 851-853)" actually refers to it. Capturing this kind of information is necessary as a first step towards an automatic classification – or at the very least characterisation – of canonical citations. Being able to classify such citations based on what they are cited for becomes more and more important as the number of references that are extracted grows.

4.7 SUMMARY

In NLP the task of capturing the named entities mentioned in a text is called NER. It consists of three steps: 1) the extraction of the named entities; 2) the detection of the relations between them and 3) the disambiguation of the extracted entities and relations. The approach I have

developed to the extraction of canonical references aligns with such a three-step process. I have defined four named entities that capture the various citation components. I have then defined a canonical citation as a binary relation between two named entities. Thus, the extraction of canonical references consists of the following steps: 1) identifying the citation components; 2) combining these components into references and 3) disambiguating these references by means of CTS URNs. A system implementing this approach was developed and evaluated against a manually corrected sample of APh abstracts. This system uses a machine learning-based approach for the first step, while the two remaining steps are implemented using a rule-based approach. The accuracy (i.e. F_1 score) of this system for each of these processing steps is: 73.88% (named entity extraction); 92.60% (relation extraction) and 73.05% (entity and relation disambiguation).

GLOSSARY

- Knowledge Base** A database containing a set of instances of the classes defined in the underlying *ontology*. A knowledge base is often employed in the context of an information extraction system as a surrogate of knowledge about a given domain. 52, 62, 63, 65, 78, 97, 100–109, 117, 118, 125, 144, 146, 150, 157, 158, 160–162, 164, 191, 198
- Linked Open Data** A set of best practices for publishing semantic data on the Web. It advocates the use of HTTP Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) as names for things and the use of links between resources and vocabularies as a way of integrating information in a machine-understandable way. 11, 66–68, 76, 83, 84, 100, 101
- Ontology** A computational artefact which models a domain of interest by defining classes of objects, their attributes and the relations between them. 43, 44, 50, 54, 60–62, 109, 198
- Opus Maximum** The only work produced by a given author or, in the case of multiple works, the most known. When citing an opus maximum the indication of the cited work can be omitted (e.g. Prop. 2.22). 52, 99, 107, 122, 123, 197, 198
- Semantic Publishing** The activity of enriching the content of publications by means of metadata expressed using semantic web standards. These metadata make it possible to discover and integrate more easily and effectively information contained within publications. 69, 73, 189

Text reuse The meaningful reiteration of text, usually beyond the mere repetition of common language. The term *text reuse* encompasses a number of different relations between texts such as translation, quotation, allusion and plagiarism. 46, 199

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